

METHODOLOGY OF MANAGEMENT OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL AND PERSONAL COMPETENCIES OF STUDENTS

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Abstract. *A competent approach to the educational process requires constant development and updating of components (methods, forms and tools). This, in turn, ensures the development of students' personal and professional competence. It can be seen that students should have a system that allows them to adequately assess their professional competencies based on various approaches to competencies.*

Keywords: *educational process, pedagogical activity, professional competence, staff of specialists, professional skills.*

Introduction. Today, special attention is paid to the introduction of interactive methods for the formation of the necessary competencies of future specialists, as well as modern paradigms of independent learning (distance learning, blended learning).

Based on world experiments, significant practical results have been achieved in the creation of a scientifically based methodological system for the implementation of the design of the professional educational process based on a competent approach in prestigious research centers in a number of developed countries. Accordingly, when training qualified personnel, it is important to change existing approaches to education and develop skills to apply the acquired theoretical knowledge in practice through independent work. It can be seen as the continuous development of the individual, the influence on global changes with his own views, the development of labor activity, the result of personality-oriented activities.

The knowledge and adaptation of the features and etiquette of teaching to them is a high stage of Education, active and self-development in education, the degree of adaptation of an individual depends on his personal and quality indicators. Improving professional competence the specifics of the factors are explained by the degree of flexibility of students to professional activities.

The level of preparation of the student for professional activity is explained by a thorough knowledge of the basic knowledge in his field, having skills and qualifications; having clear lessons and a clear plan about his future professional activity; the time of adaptability to the preparatory stage and initial knowledge of the specialist, personal qualities, the main of which is professional orientation,

Methods. At the stage of acquaintance and awareness, it is understood that the student knows information related to professional activities, distinguishes the features of the activity. When achieving this level, it is important that the norms required under sphere depend on the quality and efficiency of activity.

In the management of the development of professional and personal competencies of students, the renewal of the components of the educational process (method, form and Means)

requires their independent and systematic assimilation. This in turn promotes the growth of professional competence.

In the development of professional and personal competence, it is important to form the following personality traits in the interaction between the teacher and the student and determine their place in the educational process; such characteristics as the student's health, self-confidence, family harmony, development, collective cooperation, mutual support, material or spiritual incentive and interesting activities contribute to increasing the personal competence of students.

Special attention is required to the issues of motivation, procedural and technological support of independent cognitive activity as an integral pedagogical system that takes into account the individual interests, abilities and inclinations of students in the course of independent learning and extracurricular activities.

Independent work of students can be ensured only if there is serious and stable motivation. That is a powerful incentive is to prepare for a more effective professional activity.

Results. We cite the following active, approaches, competency, personality-oriented approaches to improving student professional competence. They depend on the content of the activity, educational methods and tools, acceptable educational material and the forms and means of training corresponding to it.

The "TABLE" method is one of the interactive methods that have a good effect on the formation of professional competence in students, serves to state thoughts in a logical sequence when performing the task given in the implementation of the method, to formulate the ability to reflect the theoretical essence of the topic under study, the issue or problem under discussion using a table. When applying it, students master the skills of a clear, concise representation of the essence of the subject (matter, problem) not in the form of an oral statement or written text, but in the table of the main idea, the basic concept, important aspects.

We recommend a sample on the application of the TABLE method in the implementation of an independent work assignment on the topic "Information Technology in professional activities "on the subject of" Information Technology".

The method "The syndicate." "Syndicate" (from the Greek. "Joint action", "brotherhood") is very useful in the formation of students' personal and professional competence when performing tasks in the classroom in a team. This method serves to educate students in the ability to creatively explore a topic (question, problem), briefly and clearly express an idea based on the generalization of theoretical knowledge, systematization.

In this method, each group must solve one task in three different ways. The essence of the topic of this task should be revealed by group 1 in the form of a diagram, group 2 in the form of a cluster, and group 3 in the form of a table. After the groups have completed the task, the solution (development) presented by them is discussed by the team.

We have developed the following tasks aimed at the formation of professional competence in the discipline "Information technology in professional activity".

1. What types of training tools can be attributed to?
2. Define "information technologies".
3. What is multimedia?
4. Give the definition of "multimedia".
5. What are the benefits of providing knowledge to students using multimedia tools?
6. What are the features of Microsoft PowerPoint?

7. At what stages is the preparation of presentation materials in the Power Point program carried out?

8. What can I use a pinball board for?

9. The benefits of using educational tools?

According to the assignment "advantages of information technology", a methodology for using the "Syndicate" method has been developed.

Task: prevention of information attacks in the educational process.

Objective: to improve the professional competence of students in specifying and using the advantages of educational tools.

Educational tools: electronic whiteboard, paper and colored markers, slide paper and special markers for writing on the slide.

Required time: 30 minutes.

The technological process of completing the task:

The teacher introduces students to the essence of the method;

Students are divided into three subgroups;

It is explained that the essence of this task topic should be disclosed by group 1 in the form of a diagram, group 2 in the form of a cluster, and group 3 in the form of a table;

The teacher explains the task, sets the amount of time (30 minutes) to complete the task.

After the specified time, each group makes a 5-minute presentation on the assignment. Explains the learning tools and their types, points out the advantages and disadvantages, and conducts a comparative analysis. After all the presentations, a discussion of the work done by small groups begins. During the discussion, the advantages and disadvantages of educational tools will be analyzed.

Conclusions and recommendations.

The transition of higher educational institutions to new educational programs, the formation of these programs in accordance with the qualification profile of specialists requires new approaches to the student's independent work. According to the new standard of higher education, up to 50% of the time required for a specialist to acquire professionally necessary knowledge and skills is allocated for independent work in the educational process. The work of small groups is analyzed by a team under the guidance of a teacher and the most qualitatively performed independent work is determined;

The teacher announces the best work based on the opinion of the team;

The teacher evaluates the work of the groups and completes the lesson.

When performing tasks on the topic, the peculiarities of their application in the process of theoretical classes, seminars, laboratory classes, pedagogical and industrial practice were touched upon. Regardless of the form in which the educational process is carried out, it serves to improve knowledge, skills and abilities in the student's personality, as well as the development of personal and professional competencies. It is aimed at training socially active qualified competitive personnel based on the free thinking of the student as a future specialist, professional self-education.

During the research, based on the analysis of scientific sources, the creative thinking of the student is revealed in order to effectively use the possibilities of realizing their activities, such as technical creativity, and consciously accepting the impact in response to integration. technical

sciences allowed us to conclude that it is necessary to form the following competencies and skills in a student:

- self-motivation (to achieve goals and activate personal abilities);
- independent organization of work (work planning, organization of personal time and space, development of technical thinking in solving problems);
- self-control (monitoring the progress of work and its intermediate results, adequate response to situations);
- self-assessment (evaluation of work results).

Based on the competence approach, based on foreign experience, the essence of the concept of "competence" is interpreted as an important cognitive, intellectual and personal conditional experience of social and professional human life. In this regard, the future specialist is encouraged to form the technical thinking of the staff, as well as to acquire the necessary competencies to carry out creative activities.

In the context of improving the technical thinking of students, as well as the competence-based approach to it of the developing educational environment, the International House-Tashkent Lyceum of the Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and Agricultural Mechanization Engineers implements a set of targeted educational influences.

It is known that technical thinking is a means of understanding technical knowledge and its technical processes. Technical thinking manifests itself in a non-standard situation, when there is a need to learn about a specific situation or subject. The development of technical thinking is the process of logical disclosure of the external and internal sides of each specific component of technology in accordance with the dynamics of bilateral human development of a specific specialization. In this process, attention is paid to professional qualities that are important for students of technical universities, the requirements for a specialist in the technical field, and the individuality of the subject of activity.

Technical thinking depends on the object of reflection, it is distinguished by the following opinions:

1. Communicative reflection concerns representations of the inner world of another person and the reasons for his actions;
2. Personal reflection analyzes one's behavior, personality image as an individual;
3. Intellectual reflection concerns knowledge about subjects, ways of personal behavior in specific situations.

Depending on the purpose of both practical and intellectual actions of technical "thinking", verification can be exploratory, executive, control and correctional-normative. Among those with intellectual abilities, it is possible to distinguish the actions of students to acquire knowledge, apply the acquired knowledge, and organize their own cognitive activities. In the process of solving problems, the following thinking actions are carried out: analyzing the problem, predicting the result, putting forward a hypothesis, checking its correctness.

Thus, the study of the characteristics of students' professional and personal competencies is an important psychological and pedagogical task, the success of which depends on the success of their formation of a high level of professional competence. The speed of technical thinking can be seen in the application of their knowledge in various situations and solving specific tasks for a limited time.

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